

Starmerella orientalis f.a., sp. nov., an ascomycetous yeast species isolated from flowers

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ABSTRACT

Four strains of a novel ascomycetous yeast species were isolated from flowers in Iran and China. Phylogenetic analysis of the sequences of the ITS region (including 5.8S rRNA gene) and the LSU rRNA gene D1/D2 domains indicated that these strains belong to the *Starmerella* clade and show divergence from previously described species in this clade. Growth reactions on carbon and nitrogen sources were similar to those observed in related species of the *Starmerella* clade. Sexual reproduction was not observed after mating tests on different sporulation media. Based on physiological characteristics and phylogeny of rRNA gene sequences, the novel species is most closely related to *Candida* (iter. nom. *Starmerella*) *powellii* and *Candida* (iter. nom. *Starmerella*) *floricola*. It is therefore assigned to the genus *Starmerella* and described as *Starmerella orientalis* f.a., sp. nov. The type strain is SAM09^T (5IBRC-M 30204^T5CBS 14142^T). The MycoBank accession number is MB 814379.